

SPIRITUAL AND MORAL VIEWS OF ABDULLA AVLONI

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Abstract: This article presents a statement of opinions on the analysis of the poetics of Abdulla Avloniy's lyrical poems. The issue of using the pedagogical heritage of Abdulla Avloni in the moral education of students is considered.

Keywords: lyric poem, jadid, poetics, poet, artistic skill, feeling, experience, lyrical hero, art, education, analysis.

Abdulla Avloniy was a prominent representative of Uzbek literature, a talented poet and playwright, teacher and public figure. The statement of Abdulla Avloniy "Education for us is a matter of life or death, salvation or death, happiness or misfortune" is also relevant in our society. [1, p.31]. As important as these words were for our nation at the beginning of the 20th century, they are just as important and relevant for us today, and maybe even more so.

He was born on July 12, 1878 in the Tashkent mahalla Merganchi, in a family of artisans. Abdulla Avloniy was able to learn from childhood. He studied the works of great Arab and Persian thinkers in the original language. The enlightener wrote in his autobiography: "When I was 12 years old, I started teaching at the madrasah in Okhal Mahalla. From the age of 14, I began to write poetry on various topics in accordance with the time ... "[1, p. 5].

In 1904, A. Avloniy founded a Jadid school in the Mirabad mahalla in Tashkent, and in 1909, a charitable society. It is believed that the word "jadid" in Arabic means "news". The main idea of the Jadids was the creation of a national-democratic state in Turkestan by raising the level of an advanced society, the socio-political and cultural consciousness of the people. The school of Abdulla Avloniy differed from the old-method schools in that all the lessons were conducted not in Arabic, but in Uzbek.

The figure tried to give more knowledge to students in such subjects as geography, history, literature, the Uzbek language, arithmetic, geometry. He reformed teaching and learning methods and created textbooks for schoolchildren, which became important spiritual events of the time. Known for such works by Avloniy as "The First Teacher", "The Second Teacher" (1912), "History", "Flourishing Land and Morality" (1913). In them, he describes the culture of other peoples, glorifies educational activities, science, encourages people to learn, gain knowledge.

Among the pedagogical works of the author, the book "Blossoming Land and Morality" is of no small importance, which reveals the methods of upbringing and education of the beginning of the last century. Reflecting on the upbringing of children as a teacher, Abdulla Avlony wrote: "If a person from childhood went the wrong way and grew up ill-mannered, then expecting something good from him is like an outstretched hand to the stars." In his opinion, the formation of moral and ethical qualities in a child is primarily influenced by the social environment, the family where he is brought up, and his environment. [4, p.105] In the history of Uzbek pedagogy, A. Avlony first described this science as "pedagogy", that is, the science of education. He divides the upbringing of children into four parts: primary education, physical education, ideological education, and moral education. In his books, the thinker urged the government to take care of the health of the younger generation. In his opinion, in order to have a healthy mindset, to develop comprehensively, one must be healthy both in mind and body. He also calls on parents to take care of the health of their children, and entrusts ideological education to teachers. "To form healthy thinking in children and continuously engage in their upbringing is a very necessary and responsible task...

Since the strength and beauty of the mind, the breadth of the worldview of children primarily depends on the teacher, "he wrote in the book" "The Second Teacher". This book of the writer is an expression of the author's ideology, here A. Avlony, through artistic images, shows such human qualities as greed, greed, greed, kindness, mercy.

Based on the specifics of our research work, we divided the poems and stories of A. Avloni into the following areas according to the peculiarities of the moral education of students:

- motherland, patriotism;
- friendship, comradeship;
- honesty;
- respect for teachers, parents and relatives;
- a call for knowledge and enlightenment - patience, contentment;
- mercy;

At the beginning of the twentieth century, many artistic and pedagogical works were written about the Motherland and patriotism. Among them, books about the Motherland and patriotism of Abdulla Avlani occupy a special place, which has not lost its significance even today. In the moral education of students, Abdulla Avloni's poems "Spring", "Summer", "Autumn", "Winter" are used; and

the poems "Motherland" and "The Word of Hijran" deserve special attention in the field of educating students in the spirit of patriotism.

In our opinion, the main reasons for choosing these works are:

- the verses "Motherland" and "The Word of Hijran" are written directly for readers and students;

- these verses correspond to the level of knowledge, worldview, age, mental state of students - the meaning and content of the verses are expressed in a simple, accessible language;

- although these poems were written almost a hundred years ago, they coincide with our today's literary language.

In his poem "Motherland" A. Avlony exalts her, saying: "Your name is sacred." He addresses the Motherland, like the Mother: Our Mother! Good mother. In you we can proudly live! [4, p. 196] Also in the work of Abdulla Avlani "Flowering Land and Morality", published in 1912, in the chapter "Love the Motherland" about the Motherland and patriotism, there are such words: "For every person, the Motherland is a place where he born and raised. Everyone loves this place more than life."

Poems by A. Avloni sing about a person, his moral beauty and his spiritual wealth, regardless of whether they are directed against heresy or superstition, or about love or school. For example, in the poem "In our country" he discusses those who do not spare money for life, but do not like even a penny for raising children, saying that "money for science does not hurt their eyes." Or in the poem "School": The school makes copper gold, The school makes you a mullah, Read, boy! [2, p.206] In this poem, the poet says that the way of salvation from oppression, injustice and lawlessness is education, school.

The thought of A. Avloni is also important for enlighteners: "Education of thought is the most important, sacred task, assigned to teachers and mentors for a long time." One of the chapters of the book "Blossoming Land and Morality" is called "Munislik".

It quotes the following verse: Yaxshi do'st aybi yor-u do'stini,
Ko'zgudek ro'baro'sida so'zlar.

Yomon o'rtog' tarog'cha ming til ila,
Orqadan birmalab terib so'zlar. [3, crp.71]

The poet reflects that a true friend is not the one who tells a person what he wants to hear. This is the person who will always tell the truth. Abdulla Avlony in almost all his textbooks paid great attention to the development of the qualities of friendship and camaraderie among students. For example, the

stories "Cooperation", "Good does not lie on the road", "The lion and the bear", "The cock and the wolf", "Ahmed and his father" in the textbook "The First Teacher"; "The Liar Friend" and "Friendship with the Bear" in the book "The Second Teacher" are prime examples in which the poet managed to reveal the true value of friendship. [3, p. 27]

In the pedagogical heritage of Abdulla Avloni, the place of poems about patience and contentment is also important. He defines patience as follows: "Patience is the ability to withstand adversity and adversity. It means setting aside immediate rewards for future blessings." Especially in the chapter "Patience" of the work "Blossoming Land and Morality" such stories as "Taksim", "Greed", "Arslan and the Bear" are printed. According to Avlani, "education of the mind is the most important, the most precious, the most sacred." In his works, the figure criticizes the backwardness and ignorance of his time and calls people to knowledge and enlightenment. This issue is considered in detail in the chapters "Knowledge", "Aksami ilm", "Fatonat", "Hifzi Lison", "Ignorance", "Justice" of the textbook "Flowering land and morality". The poems and stories of Abdullah Avlani, calling people to knowledge and enlightenment, are an important means of moral education. In his works he showed the importance of education and knowledge.

The works of A. Avlani make the reader think and encourage self-education, because his works show the true face of a person. These works are still of great importance in the formation of national self-consciousness and morality among students. In our society, the education of young people is recognized as the most important issue, and serious efforts are being made in this direction. In particular, the process of education and upbringing is one of the most pressing issues.

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